

1 Orientation-Aware Refinement of the DTI-ALPS Index

2 Scott N. Hwang^{a,*}, Gavin Jones^a, Numa Mubin^a, Jack Quillen^a, Sangam
3 G. Kanekar^a

*^aPennsylvania State University College of Medicine, Department of
Radiology, Hershey, PA, USA*

4 Abstract

The diffusion tensor imaging along perivascular spaces (DTI-ALPS) index is a non-invasive marker related to perivascular diffusion, but its reliance on fixed scanner-aligned axes makes it sensitive to head tilt and anatomical variability. We describe a refinement that computes directional diffusivities along subject-specific axes derived from tract directions in the classical ALPS regions of interest. The calculation is stabilized with fractional anisotropy-weighted tract averaging, sign consistency, and quality checks. Rotation simulation using real diffusion data confirms that classic ALPS depends on head orientation while the refined method is mathematically invariant. To confirm the method works as intended, it was applied to compute the classic and corrected ALPS metrics for $n = 62$ Dallas Lifespan Brain Study sessions. All ALPS variants reproduce the established negative association with age. This drop-in replacement reduces orientation-driven variance without changing what ALPS measures, requiring only closed-form operations without template registration or iterative algorithms.

5 *Keywords:* diffusion tensor imaging, DTI-ALPS, perivascular diffusion,
6 orientation correction, neuroimaging methods

7 1. Introduction

8 The DTI-ALPS index, originally proposed as a non-invasive probe of
9 perivascular diffusion [1], has been adopted in over 500 published studies
10 spanning Alzheimer’s disease, Parkinson’s disease, cerebral small vessel dis-
11 ease, traumatic brain injury, depression, and normal aging. A Bayesian
12 meta-analysis confirmed that the index consistently distinguishes patients
13 with Alzheimer’s and Parkinson’s disease from healthy controls [2], and it

*Corresponding author.

Email address: snh5391@psu.edu (Scott N. Hwang)

14 has shown significant associations with clinical severity across these and
 15 other conditions. However, the biological interpretation of DTI-ALPS has
 16 shifted substantially. Taoka, the originator of the method, cautioned in a
 17 2024 review that a decreased ALPS index should not be equated with “glym-
 18 phatic dysfunction” [3]. More recently, Mossige et al. compared DTI-ALPS
 19 with intrathecal contrast-enhanced MRI, the current reference standard, and
 20 found no association between the ALPS index and glymphatic function. CSF
 21 tracer enrichment in the ALPS regions of interest was sparse [4]. Converging
 22 evidence suggests the index primarily reflects white matter microstructural
 23 properties rather than fluid clearance [3, 4, 2]. Nonetheless, the metric re-
 24 mains widely used and clinically informative. Methodological improvements
 25 that reduce measurement noise are therefore valuable regardless of what bi-
 26 ological property the index ultimately captures.

27 The ALPS index quantifies diffusivity along putative perivascular space
 28 (PVS) directions relative to tract-constrained diffusivity in projection and
 29 association fibers near the lateral ventricles. Classic ALPS assumes projec-
 30 tion fibers run superior–inferior (z), association fibers anterior–posterior (y),
 31 and PVS left–right (x):

$$\text{ALPS} = \frac{D_x^{\text{proj}} + D_x^{\text{assoc}}}{D_y^{\text{proj}} + D_z^{\text{assoc}}}.$$

32 This ties computation to laboratory coordinates, making it susceptible to
 33 head tilt and anatomical variability. Prior work has addressed this through
 34 template-space reorientation using vector registration [5], principal-axis de-
 35 composition (ALPS-PAS) [6], and voxelwise local diffusion directions (LD-
 36 ALPS) [7]. We propose a simpler alternative that keeps the classic ratio
 37 but replaces fixed axes with subject-specific, anatomically derived axes using
 38 only closed-form operations.

39 The refinement is conceptually simple:

- 40 1. Use diffusivity along the *actual* principal direction of projection fibers
 41 instead of assuming alignment with z
- 42 2. Use diffusivity along the *actual* principal direction of association fibers
 43 instead of assuming y
- 44 3. Estimate the PVS direction as the cross-product of both tract directions
- 45 4. Apply the usual ALPS ratio formula using these subject-specific axes

Figure 1: Orientation-aware ALPS concept. (a) DEC-FA map with example ROIs. (b) Projection (blue) and association (green) fibers, perivascular spaces (black), and scanner axes. Head tilt changes tract orientation in scanner space; the refined method evaluates along a subject-specific triad.

46 2. Methods

47 In plain terms, classic DTI-ALPS assumes every brain is perfectly aligned
 48 with the scanner. Projection fibers are taken to run straight superior–inferior
 49 (the scanner z -axis), association fibers anterior–posterior (the y -axis), and
 50 perivascular spaces left–right (the x -axis). When the head is tilted, or when
 51 an individual’s white-matter tracts simply do not align with these direc-
 52 tions, the index changes even though the underlying biology has not. The
 53 refinement is to measure rather than assume. The principal eigenvector at
 54 each voxel already points along the local fiber direction, so we average those
 55 vectors (FA-weighted) within each ROI to obtain the actual projection-fiber
 56 and association-fiber directions for that subject. The perivascular axis is
 57 then simply the cross product of the two vectors, which is the direction per-
 58 pendicular to both fiber tracts. The same Taoka ratio is then evaluated along
 59 these subject-specific axes rather than the scanner axes. No registration, no
 60 atlas, and no iterative fitting is required, only three averages and a cross
 61 product. Conceptually, the method can be explained in one sentence: use
 62 the directions the fibers actually point in, rather than assuming they line up
 63 with the scanner.

64 In the following, we mathematically formalize the replacement of the
 65 fixed scanner axes with subject-specific anatomical directions derived from
 66 the diffusion tensor in each ROI.

67 *2.1. ROI Definition and Filtering*

68 Standard ALPS ROIs in the superior corona radiata (SCR; projection
69 fibers) and superior longitudinal fasciculus (SLF; association fibers) [1] are
70 manually drawn on DEC-FA images using software implemented with a
71 Python/FastAPI backend and a React/TypeScript browser interface.

72 Only voxels with $FA \geq FA_{\text{thr}}$ (default 0.2) are retained in each ROI:

$$\Omega_{\text{SCR}} = \{i \in \text{ROI}_{\text{proj}} : FA_i \geq FA_{\text{thr}}\}, \quad \Omega_{\text{SLF}} = \{i \in \text{ROI}_{\text{assoc}} : FA_i \geq FA_{\text{thr}}\}.$$

73 If either $|\Omega_{\text{SCR}}| = 0$ or $|\Omega_{\text{SLF}}| = 0$ after thresholding, computation is aborted.
74 Voxels with undefined eigenvalues are excluded from all subsequent calcula-
75 tions. An optional FA cap percentile can be applied to reduce outlier influ-
76 ence.

77 *2.2. Tract Directions (FA-Weighted Mean)*

78 Extract the first eigenvector $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i}$ and FA_i at each voxel. Because eigenvec-
79 tors have \pm sign ambiguity, we enforce sign consistency using a running mean:
80 starting from $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1,1}$, each subsequent vector $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i}$ is flipped if $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1:i-1} < 0$.
81 The FA-weighted mean directions are:

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{proj}} = \frac{\sum_{i \in \text{SCR}} FA_i \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i}}{\left\| \sum_{i \in \text{SCR}} FA_i \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i} \right\|}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{assoc}} = \frac{\sum_{i \in \text{SLF}} FA_i \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i}}{\left\| \sum_{i \in \text{SLF}} FA_i \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i} \right\|}.$$

82 *2.3. PVS Axis and Orthogonal Axes*

83 Define a common perivascular axis:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}} = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{proj}} \times \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{assoc}}}{\left\| \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{proj}} \times \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{assoc}} \right\|}.$$

84 Construct the axis orthogonal to both local tract and PVS:

$$\hat{\mathbf{o}}_{\text{proj}} = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{p}} \times \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{proj}}}{\left\| \hat{\mathbf{p}} \times \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{proj}} \right\|}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{o}}_{\text{assoc}} = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{p}} \times \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{assoc}}}{\left\| \hat{\mathbf{p}} \times \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{assoc}} \right\|}.$$

85 *2.4. Directional Diffusivities*

86 For unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ and tensor $\mathbf{D}_i = \mathbf{V}_i \text{diag}(\lambda_{1,i}, \lambda_{2,i}, \lambda_{3,i}) \mathbf{V}_i^T$, the direc-
87 tional diffusivity is:

$$D_i(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) = \hat{\mathbf{u}}^T \mathbf{D}_i \hat{\mathbf{u}} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \lambda_{k,i} (\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{k,i} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{u}})^2.$$

88 The ROI-mean directional diffusivity is $D_{\text{ROI}}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i \in \text{ROI}} D_i(\hat{\mathbf{u}})$.

89 *2.5. Refined ALPS Index*

$$\boxed{\text{ALPS}_{\text{refined}} = \frac{D_{\text{SCR}}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}) + D_{\text{SLF}}(\hat{\mathbf{p}})}{D_{\text{SCR}}(\hat{\mathbf{o}}_{\text{proj}}) + D_{\text{SLF}}(\hat{\mathbf{o}}_{\text{assoc}})}}$$

90 When projection $\parallel z$ and association $\parallel y$, this reduces to classic ALPS.

91 When bilateral ROIs are drawn, computation can be performed per-
92 hemisphere by splitting at the mid-sagittal plane.

93 *2.6. ALPS-PAS: Principal Axis Sorting*

94 For comparison, we also implement the ALPS-PAS method of Ajouz et
95 al. [6]. Rather than computing directional diffusivities along specified axes,
96 ALPS-PAS uses the secondary eigenvalues (λ_2, λ_3) directly, with assignment
97 based on the x -alignment of their corresponding eigenvectors at each voxel:

$$(\lambda_x, \lambda_{\neg x})_i = \begin{cases} (\lambda_{2,i}, \lambda_{3,i}) & \text{if } |v_{2,i}^{(x)}| > |v_{3,i}^{(x)}|, \\ (\lambda_{3,i}, \lambda_{2,i}) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

98 The ALPS-PAS index is:

$$\text{ALPS}_{\text{PAS}} = \frac{\langle \lambda_x \rangle_{\text{proj}} + \langle \lambda_x \rangle_{\text{assoc}}}{\langle \lambda_{\neg x} \rangle_{\text{proj}} + \langle \lambda_{\neg x} \rangle_{\text{assoc}}}.$$

99 *2.7. Further Refinement via Local v_2 - v_3 Projection*

100 The cross-product PVS axis $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{\times}$ is perpendicular to ROI-mean tract di-
101 rections but not necessarily to the local fiber $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i}$ at each voxel. We address
102 this by projecting $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{\times}$ onto the transverse plane at each voxel:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i = (\mathbf{I} - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i} \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i}^{\top}) \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{\times}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{p}}_i = \frac{\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i\|}.$$

103 An FA-weighted mean over the combined SCR and SLF voxels (per hemi-
104 sphere) yields a single Refined+ PVS axis:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}^{(+)} = \frac{\sum_{i \in \text{SCRUSLF}} \text{FA}_i \hat{\mathbf{p}}_i}{\left\| \sum_{i \in \text{SCRUSLF}} \text{FA}_i \hat{\mathbf{p}}_i \right\|}.$$

105 The orthogonal axes $\hat{\mathbf{o}}_{\text{proj}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{o}}_{\text{assoc}}$ are then recomputed by substituting
106 $\hat{\mathbf{p}}^{(+)}$ for $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ in the cross-product expressions above, and the boxed Refined
107 ALPS formula is evaluated using these refined axes to obtain the Refined+
108 index.

109 *2.8. Quality Control*

110 Voxel-level filtering uses only the $FA \geq FA_{thr}$ criterion of §2.1. Com-
111 putation is aborted only when an ROI is empty after FA thresholding, or
112 when the cross product of the mean tract directions is numerically degen-
113 erate ($\|\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{proj} \times \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{assoc}\| < 10^{-10}$); in the latter case the PVS axis falls back
114 to the scanner x -axis, a condition that does not arise for anatomically rea-
115 sonable ROIs in vivo. Stricter ill-conditioning thresholds (e.g., requiring
116 $|\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{proj} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{assoc}| < 0.5$ or $\|\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{proj} \times \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{assoc}\| > 10^{-3}$) were considered but excluded
117 too many otherwise-usable sessions and were not adopted. Diagnostic qual-
118 ity metrics reported per session and per ROI include voxel counts, mean
119 FA, the inter-fiber angle $\theta = \arccos|\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{proj} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{assoc}|$, the Refined+ FA-weighted
120 resultant length R (a directional dispersion measure, with $R \rightarrow 1$ when per-
121 voxel projected PVS directions agree), and the agreement angle $\Delta\phi$ between
122 the cross-product and Refined+ PVS axes. Session-level QC applied to the
123 cohort analysis (motion and FA dropout) is described in §2.9.

124 *2.9. Rotation Simulation Protocol*

125 For rotation matrix \mathbf{R} , tensors transform as $\mathbf{D}' = \mathbf{RDR}^T$. We applied
126 rotations about each axis over $\pm 30^\circ$ in 5° increments and computed Classic
127 ALPS, Refined ALPS, Refined+ ALPS, and ALPS-PAS at each angle.

128 *2.10. Age Correlation Analysis*

129 We used publicly available diffusion data from the Dallas Lifespan Brain
130 Study (DLBS; OpenNeuro accession ds004856, version 1.2.0) [9], a longitudi-
131 nal aging cohort of 462 unique participants imaged across up to three waves,
132 ages 21–91 years. DTI fitting used the $b = 1000$ s/mm² shell (30 diffu-
133 sion directions plus a single $b = 0$ volume per acquisition), with ROIs drawn
134 manually on DEC-FA maps in the superior corona radiata (projection fibers)
135 and superior longitudinal fasciculus (association fibers) on both hemispheres.
136 Complete cases with non-missing age and non-missing left and right values
137 for all four metrics were retained ($n = 81$). We then applied two objec-
138 tive quality-control criteria: (i) sessions with mean absolute subject motion
139 (eddy-corrected RMS displacement) exceeding 0.5 mm were excluded to re-
140 move scans with severe within-acquisition motion, and (ii) sessions in which
141 more than 20% of voxels within the manually drawn ROIs failed the FA
142 > 0.2 criterion were excluded, as this indicates ROI placement on anatomy
143 with inadequate white-matter anisotropy. After QC, $n = 62$ sessions re-
144 mained. Associations with age were evaluated using Pearson correlation,

145 with Benjamini–Hochberg FDR correction ($m = 4$ tests). This study used
146 only publicly available, de-identified data; no additional ethical approval was
147 required.

148 **3. Results**

149 *3.1. Rotation Simulation*

150 To demonstrate coordinate-system invariance, we simulated head rotation
151 using real DTI data. From a single acquisition with manually placed supe-
152 rior corona radiata (SCR) and superior longitudinal fasciculus (SLF) ROIs
153 (Fig. 2), we applied synthetic rotations to all tensors and recomputed ALPS
154 at each angle.

155 Figure 3 shows the four ALPS variants computed at each rotation angle.
156 Refined and Refined+ are mathematically invariant to rotation about all
157 three axes (variation $< 0.1\%$, at the numerical-precision floor). ALPS-PAS
158 is invariant to X-axis rotation by construction, since its eigenvalue assignment
159 depends on x -components that are unchanged by rotation about x , but it is
160 not strictly invariant to Y- or Z-axis rotation. Classic ALPS depends on head
161 orientation. Specific shapes and amplitudes are subject-specific and shown
162 for illustration only.

163 *3.2. Association with Age in a Lifespan Cohort*

164 For each participant, we computed a combined ALPS value as the left–
165 right average for each metric, $\text{ALPS}_{\text{avg}} = (\text{ALPS}_L + \text{ALPS}_R)/2$. To ensure
166 identical sample composition across metrics, we restricted the analysis to
167 complete cases with non-missing age and non-missing left and right values
168 for all four combined metrics (Classic, Refined, Refined+, and ALPS-PAS),
169 yielding $n = 81$ complete cases. Of these, we further excluded sessions with
170 excessive eddy-corrected subject motion (mean absolute RMS displacement
171 > 0.5 mm) or with more than 20% of ROI voxels below the FA threshold of
172 0.2, leaving $n = 62$ sessions for analysis. We evaluated associations with age
173 using Pearson correlation. To account for multiple testing across the four a
174 priori combined metrics, we applied the Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery
175 rate (FDR) procedure with $m = 4$ tests and report FDR-adjusted q -values.

176 All four combined metrics showed significant negative associations with
177 age (Fig. 4), with moderate effect sizes (Pearson r ranging from -0.46 to
178 -0.48) and slopes of approximately -0.005 to -0.006 ALPS units per year

Figure 2: DEC-FA map (axial slice) with manually drawn ROIs outlined in white. The medial pair of ROIs (immediately lateral to the lateral ventricles, on the predominantly blue projection fibers) marks the superior corona radiata (SCR); the lateral pair (on the predominantly green association fibers) marks the superior longitudinal fasciculus (SLF). Color encodes principal diffusion direction (red = left–right, green = anterior–posterior, blue = superior–inferior). Left hemisphere ROIs from a single acquisition were used for the rotation simulation.

179 (Table 1). After FDR correction across the four combined metrics, all re-
 180 mained highly significant ($q < 0.001$).

181 Classic ALPS yielded the numerically strongest association ($r = -0.478$),
 182 followed by ALPS-PAS ($r = -0.470$), Refined ($r = -0.461$), and Refined+
 183 ($r = -0.456$). The orientation-aware methods by design discard scanner-
 184 frame coordinate information in exchange for robustness to head-tilt and
 185 anatomical misalignment. The modest reduction in effect size for the refined
 186 methods ($\Delta r \approx 0.05$) is small compared with the ~ 30 – 50% variation in-
 187 duced by $\pm 30^\circ$ rotation under Classic ALPS (Fig. 3a). Notably, this small
 188 Classic advantage persists despite substantial scanner-anatomic axis devia-

Metric	n	Pearson r	p	BH-FDR q
Classic (L/R avg)	62	-0.478	0.000084	0.00020
Refined (L/R avg)	62	-0.461	0.000165	0.00020
Refined+ (L/R avg)	62	-0.456	0.000198	0.00020
ALPS-PAS (L/R avg)	62	-0.470	0.000114	0.00020

Table 1: Associations between age and combined DTI-ALPS metrics computed as left-right averages. Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) FDR correction was applied across the four pre-specified combined metrics ($m = 4$).

189 tion in the cohort (Section 3.3). Per-subject Classic-Refined differences track
190 that deviation, indicating the bias is real on a per-subject basis even when
191 its net effect on a cross-sectional age regression is small. The purpose of the
192 age analysis is not to demonstrate improved effect sizes but to confirm that
193 the refined indices preserve known biological associations. The benefit of
194 orientation correction would be most apparent in datasets with even greater
195 variability in head positioning, for example, clinical acquisitions, multi-site
196 studies, or pediatric populations, where consistent positioning is difficult.

197 3.3. Scanner-Anatomic Axis Deviation in the Lifespan Cohort

198 To quantify how much the fixed scanner axes used by Classic DTI-ALPS
199 deviate from the anatomically-defined axes used by the refined method, we
200 computed three deviation angles per session and per hemisphere on the
201 same $n = 62$ post-QC sessions used in the age analysis: θ_{PVS} between
202 the cross-product PVS axis $\hat{p} = v_{\text{proj}} \times v_{\text{assoc}}$ and scanner \hat{x} ; θ_{SCR} between
203 the projection-tract direction v_{proj} and scanner \hat{z} ; and θ_{SLF} between the
204 association-tract direction v_{assoc} and scanner \hat{y} . Each angle was the acute
205 angle (range 0-90°) between two unit vectors, accounting for the antipodal
206 symmetry of diffusion eigenvectors.

207 Pooled across left and right hemispheres, the SCR fiber direction deviated
208 from scanner- \hat{z} by a median of 15.5° (IQR [10.5°, 19.1°], max 77.4°); the
209 cross-product PVS axis deviated from scanner- \hat{x} by a median of 9.8° (IQR
210 [5.9°, 14.6°], max 72.8°); and the SLF axis deviated from scanner- \hat{y} by a
211 median of 9.5° (IQR [6.7°, 14.6°], max 72.4°) (Fig. 5A). The per-subject
212 mean PVS deviation correlated positively with the absolute Classic-Refined
213 ALPS difference ($r = +0.46$, $p = 1.4 \times 10^{-4}$, slope ≈ 0.003 ALPS units per
214 degree), confirming that the orientation correction has the largest impact
215 on subjects whose scanner frame is most tilted relative to the underlying

216 tract anatomy (Fig. 5B). Even in this carefully acquired research cohort,
 217 the scanner axes routinely deviate from anatomy by 10–20° with a long tail
 218 extending past 70°, providing a direct empirical motivation for orientation
 219 correction independent of the rotation simulation.

220 4. Discussion

221 The refined methods achieve complete coordinate-system invariance—a
 222 mathematical consequence of deriving measurement axes from tensor data.
 223 Classic ALPS assumes projection fibers are parallel to z , association fibers
 224 parallel to y , and PVS parallel to x ; deviations from these assumptions in-
 225 troduce variable error across subjects and sessions.

226	Method	Orientation Error	Estimation Error	Invariant Axes
	Classic ALPS	Variable (all axes)	None	None
227	ALPS-PAS	Variable (y, z axes)	None	x only
	Refined ALPS	None (invariant)	Fixed (if PVS biased)	All
	Refined+ ALPS	None (invariant)	Fixed (reduced)	All

228 This trade-off favors the refined approach: longitudinal studies bene-
 229 fit from consistent values across sessions; cross-subject comparisons reflect
 230 anatomy rather than positioning; multi-site studies gain statistical power
 231 from reduced variance.

232 Classic ALPS depends on head orientation, with rotation-induced varia-
 233 tion that can be comparable to or exceed reported disease-related differences
 234 (typically 5–20%). The refined methods eliminate this orientation-dependent
 235 artifact entirely.

236 The simulation demonstrates invariance but not accuracy; true valida-
 237 tion would require comparison against an independent measure of whatever
 238 biological process DTI-ALPS reflects. The refined method’s claim is delib-
 239 erately modest: it measures the same quantity as classic ALPS, but without
 240 orientation-dependent artifacts.

241 Our method prioritizes eliminating variable orientation-dependent error
 242 over maximizing absolute accuracy. If the cross-product PVS axis introduces
 243 systematic bias relative to true perivascular anatomy, this manifests as a fixed
 244 offset rather than variable artifact—a favorable trade-off for longitudinal and
 245 multi-site studies where consistency matters more than absolute calibration.

246 Regardless of orientation correction, a decreased DTI-ALPS value should
247 not be interpreted as direct evidence of glymphatic dysfunction. Taoka’s
248 2024 review explicitly recommends reporting “decreased ALPS index” rather
249 than “glymphatic dysfunction” [3], and the intrathecal contrast study by
250 Mossige et al. found no association between the ALPS index and reference-
251 standard measures of glymphatic function [4]. The index likely reflects white
252 matter microstructural properties, with changes potentially indicating fiber
253 disorganization or pathological protein deposition rather than impaired fluid
254 clearance [8]. The orientation correction we propose is valuable precisely
255 because it improves measurement consistency regardless of what biological
256 property the ALPS index captures.

257 *4.1. Comparison with Related Methods*

258 Several methods address orientation dependence in DTI-ALPS. Burles
259 et al. found that more than 85% of published DTI-ALPS studies use un-
260 corrected methods vulnerable to head orientation bias [7]. Tatekawa et al.
261 used FSL’s `vecreg` to register diffusion vectors to template space, demon-
262 strating improved intra- and inter-rater reliability ($ICC > 0.85$ vs. 0.52–0.81)
263 on the OASIS-3 dataset [5]. Burles et al. introduced LD-ALPS, computing
264 voxelwise local diffusion directions using DBSCAN clustering and interpola-
265 tion [7]. These methods achieve orientation invariance but require template
266 registration infrastructure or iterative algorithms.

267 Ajouz et al. proposed ALPS-PAS, which forms ratios of the eigenval-
268 ues λ_2 and λ_3 with assignment based on the x -component of each eigen-
269 vector [6]. Our method similarly operates in native space, requiring only
270 FA-weighted vector averaging and a cross-product. While ALPS-PAS of-
271 fers voxelwise operation without requiring tract-mean computation, it is not
272 strictly orientation-invariant. The eigenvalue assignment rule depends on
273 eigenvector orientation in the laboratory frame, and rotations around the y -
274 or z -axis can alter the assignment and thus the index. Our method achieves
275 true orientation invariance because both the diffusion tensor and the mea-
276 surement axes are defined in the same anatomical frame and rotate identically
277 with head position.

278 *4.2. Limitations*

279 Like classic ALPS, eigenvectors can be unstable at low FA. The ap-
280 proach assumes near-orthogonality of SCR and SLF. Departures reduce inter-
281 pretability. The refinement reduces orientation variance but does not change

282 what ALPS measures. Recent evidence suggests the index reflects white
283 matter microstructure rather than glymphatic clearance [3, 4], but the ori-
284 entation correction remains applicable regardless of the underlying biological
285 substrate. The age analysis was designed to confirm that the method works,
286 i.e., that the orientation-aware refinement reproduces the well-established
287 negative association between DTI-ALPS and age, rather than to rigorously
288 characterize age-related changes. We manually annotated SCR and SLF
289 ROIs on 81 Dallas Lifespan Brain Study sessions, of which 62 also passed the
290 pre-specified motion and FA quality criteria; this was sufficient to recover the
291 age association (Fig. 4) for all four ALPS variants. Replication on a larger
292 and more orientation-variable cohorts would strengthen these findings and
293 could reveal whether orientation correction improves effect sizes in samples
294 with greater head-positioning variability.

295 **5. Conclusion**

296 Replacing fixed axes with a subject-specific triad derived from tensor
297 eigenvectors eliminates ALPS sensitivity to head tilt. Classic ALPS depends
298 on head orientation; the Refined and Refined+ methods are fully invariant to
299 rotation about all axes, while ALPS-PAS achieves invariance only about the
300 x -axis. This drop-in replacement requires only FA-weighted averaging and
301 a cross-product, making it a straightforward improvement for longitudinal,
302 cross-subject, and multi-site studies.

303 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

304 **Scott N. Hwang:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal
305 analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft,
306 Writing – review & editing. **Gavin Jones:** Investigation, Writing – review
307 & editing. **Numa Mubin:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Jack**
308 **Quillen:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Sangam G. Kanekar:**
309 Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

310 **Acknowledgements**

311 This research used data from the Dallas Lifespan Brain Study (DLBS),
312 distributed via OpenNeuro (accession ds004856). We thank the DLBS inves-
313 tigators and participants for making these data publicly available.

314 **Funding**

315 This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in
316 the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

317 **Declaration of competing interest**

318 The authors declare no competing interests.

319 **Data availability**

320 The Dallas Lifespan Brain Study dataset used in this study is publicly
321 available from OpenNeuro (<https://openneuro.org/datasets/ds004856>,
322 version 1.2.0). A software implementation of the orientation-aware refine-
323 ment (Refined and Refined+ methods) is available at [https://github.com/
324 snhwang/dti-alps-refined](https://github.com/snhwang/dti-alps-refined). A preprint of this manuscript is available on
325 Zenodo (doi:10.5281/zenodo.20060435).

326 **Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the**
327 **manuscript preparation process**

328 During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Claude Code (An-
329 thropic) substantially for assistance with developing the analysis and figure-
330 generation code and with drafting and language editing of the manuscript,
331 and Perplexity.ai to a lesser extent for summarizing prior literature and sup-
332 porting background research. After using these tools, the author(s) reviewed
333 and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the con-
334 tent of the published article.

335 **References**

- 336 [1] Taoka T, Masutani Y, Kawai H, Nakane T, Matsuoka K, Yasuno F, et
337 al (2017) Evaluation of glymphatic system activity with the diffusion
338 MR technique: diffusion tensor image analysis along the perivascular
339 space (DTI-ALPS) in Alzheimer’s disease cases. *Jpn J Radiol* 35:172–178.
340 <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11604-017-0617-Z/>

- 341 [2] Costa T, Manuello J, Premi E, Mattioli I, Lasagna L, Lahoz CB, et
342 al. Evaluating the robustness of DTI-ALPS in clinical context: a meta-
343 analytic parallel on Alzheimer’s and Parkinson’s diseases. *Sci Rep.* 2024
344 Nov 2;14(1):26381.
- 345 [3] Taoka T, Ito R, Nakamichi R, Nakane T, Kawai H, Naganawa S. Diffu-
346 sion Tensor Image Analysis ALong the Perivascular Space (DTI-ALPS):
347 Revisiting the Meaning and Significance of the Method. *Magn Reson Med*
348 *Sci.* 2024 Jul 1;23(3):268-290.
- 349 [4] Mossige I, Valnes LM, Storås TH, Emblem KE, Eide PK, Ringstad
350 G. Comparing Glymphatic Function Measures: Diffusion Tensor Im-
351 age Analysis Along Perivascular Spaces (DTI-ALPS) versus Intrathecal
352 Contrast-Enhanced MRI. *Radiology.* 2026 Feb;318(2):e252070.
- 353 [5] Tatekawa H, Matsushita S, Ueda D, Takita H, Horiuchi D, Atsukawa N,
354 et al. Improved reproducibility of diffusion tensor image analysis along
355 the perivascular space (DTI-ALPS) index: an analysis of reorientation
356 technique of the OASIS-3 dataset. *Jpn J Radiol.* 2023 Apr;41(4):393-400.
- 357 [6] Ajouz A, Jansen O, Frohwein LJ, Seehafer S, Larsen N, Hövener JB.
358 Automatic determination of glymphatic flow with the DTI-ALPS-index
359 along the principal axis system in native imaging space corrects for head
360 and fiber orientation. *Magn Reson Med.* 2026 Feb;95(2):1110-1122.
- 361 [7] Burles F, Sallis E, Kopala-Sibley DC, Iaria G. Mitigating head position
362 bias in perivascular fluid imaging: LD-ALPS, a novel method for DTI-
363 ALPS calculation. *NeuroSci* 2025;6:101.
- 364 [8] Schilling KG, Newton A, Tax C, Nilsson M, Chamberland M, Anderson
365 A, et al. White Matter Geometry Confounds Diffusion Tensor Imaging
366 Along Perivascular Space (DTI-ALPS) Measures. *Hum Brain Mapp.* 2025
367 Jul;46(10):e70282.
- 368 [9] Park D, Hennessee J, Smith ET, Chan M, Katen C, Bacci J, et
369 al. The Dallas Lifespan Brain Study [Dataset]. *OpenNeuro* 2023.
370 doi:10.18112/openneuro.ds004856.v1.2.0.

Figure 3: ALPS vs. rotation angle for one representative session. Lines: Classic (blue solid), ALPS-PAS (cyan dashed), Refined (orange solid), Refined+ (pink dashed). (a) X-axis rotation (nodding). (b) Y-axis rotation (turning). (c) Z-axis rotation (tilting).

Figure 4: Correlations between age and combined DTI-ALPS metrics (left–right averages), restricted to complete cases passing motion and FA quality-control criteria ($n = 62$). Each panel shows the least-squares regression line and an inset reporting Pearson r , p , and the slope (ALPS units/year). (a) Classic ALPS. (b) Refined ALPS. (c) Refined+ ALPS. (d) ALPS-PAS.

Figure 5: Scanner versus anatomic axis deviation in the Dallas Lifespan Brain Study cohort ($n = 62$ post-QC sessions). **(A)** Distributions of θ_{PVS} , θ_{SCR} , and θ_{SLF} pooled across left and right hemispheres ($2 \times 62 = 124$ measurements per angle); dashed lines indicate medians. The SCR fiber direction is the most-tilted axis. **(B)** Per-subject absolute difference between Classic and Refined ALPS plotted against the per-subject mean θ_{PVS} (left-right average); subjects with greater PVS-axis deviation show larger Classic-vs-Refined disagreement (Pearson $r = +0.46$, $p = 1.4 \times 10^{-4}$).